

DESIGN AND PRODUCTION OF FILAMENT WOUND SLEEVES FOR HIGH SPEED FLYWHEEL ROTORS

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Composite flywheel energy storage system

Mechanical properties for various winding tensions

HS4 Fiber/ FC-25						
S/MPa	X(NOL)	X _c (0°)	X _c (90°)	Y _c (90°)	Y _c (0°)	S
	1576.04	1557.27	952.31	38.75	137.89	70.58
E/GPa	E(NOL)	E _{Xc} (0°)	E _{Xc} (90°)	E _{Yc} (90°)	E _{Yc} (0°)	G
	61.70	65.43	53.42	8.10	7.96	4.51

T800 Fiber/ FC-25						
S/MPa	X(NOL)	X _c (0°)	X _c (90°)	Y _c (90°)	Y _c (0°)	S
	2531.64	2506.38	1354.21	60.03	167.89	91.33
E/GPa	E(NOL)	E _{Xc} (0°)	E _{Xc} (90°)	E _{Yc} (90°)	E _{Yc} (0°)	G
	151.09	155.21	149.61	9.22	8.82	5.01

Winding with normal tension (30N)

Winding with high tension (100N)

Composite flywheel – Stress & strain analysis

Composite flywheel – Finite element model

Equilibrium equation:

Stresses and strains of steel spindle and Al hub:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_r^i \\ \sigma_\theta^i \\ \sigma_z^i \\ \tau_{rz}^i \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E_i}{1-\nu_i^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu_i & \nu_i \\ \nu_i & 1 & \nu_i \\ \nu_i & \nu_i & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_r^i \\ \epsilon_\theta^i \\ \epsilon_z^i \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{cases} \epsilon_r^i = \frac{u_r^i}{r} \\ \epsilon_\theta^i = \frac{u_\theta^i}{r} \\ \epsilon_z^i = \frac{du_z^i}{dz} \end{cases}$$

$$u_r^i = -\rho\omega^2 C_1^i r^3 + C_2^i r + C_3^i r^{-1}$$

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_r^i = \frac{E_i C_1^i}{1-\nu_i} - \frac{E_i C_2^i}{(1+\nu_i)r^2} - \frac{E_i(3+\nu_i)\rho\omega^2 C_1^i r^2}{1-\nu_i} \\ \sigma_\theta^i = \frac{E_i C_1^i}{1-\nu_i} + \frac{E_i C_2^i}{(1+\nu_i)r^2} - \frac{E_i(1+3\nu_i)\rho\omega^2 C_1^i r^2}{1-\nu_i} \\ \sigma_z^i = -3\rho\omega^2 C_1^i r^2 + C_3^i - C_2^i r^{-2} \\ \epsilon_\theta^i = -\rho\omega^2 C_1^i r^2 + C_3^i + C_2^i r^{-2} \end{cases}$$

Stresses and strains of composite flange:

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + \rho r \omega^2 = 0$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_r^i \\ \sigma_\theta^i \\ \sigma_z^i \\ \tau_{rz}^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}^i & Q_{12}^i & Q_{13}^i \\ Q_{21}^i & Q_{22}^i & Q_{23}^i \\ Q_{31}^i & Q_{32}^i & Q_{33}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_r^i \\ \epsilon_\theta^i \\ \epsilon_z^i \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{cases} \epsilon_r^i = \frac{u_r^i}{r} \\ \epsilon_\theta^i = \frac{u_\theta^i}{r} \\ \epsilon_z^i = \frac{du_z^i}{dz} \end{cases}$$

$$E_1^i r^2 \frac{d^2 u_r^i}{dr^2} + E_1^i r \frac{du_r^i}{dr} - E_\theta^i u_r^i = -\rho^i \omega^2 (1 - \nu_{r\theta}^i) r^3$$

$$\begin{cases} u_r^i = -\rho^i \omega^2 \gamma_0^i r^3 + C_1^i r^{\kappa^i} + C_2^i r^{-\kappa^i} \\ \sigma_r^i = -\rho^i \omega^2 \gamma_1^i r^2 + C_1^i \gamma_2^i r^{\kappa^i-1} + C_2^i \gamma_3^i r^{-\kappa^i-1} \\ \sigma_\theta^i = -\rho^i \omega^2 \gamma_4^i r^2 + C_1^i \gamma_5^i r^{\kappa^i-1} + C_2^i \gamma_6^i r^{-\kappa^i-1} \end{cases}$$

式 中: $\kappa^i = \sqrt{Q_{11}^i/Q_{33}^i}$ $\gamma_0^i = 1/(9 - \kappa^i)^2$ $\gamma_1^i = (Q_{13}^i + 3Q_{33}^i)\gamma_0^i$
 $\gamma_2^i = Q_{13}^i + \kappa^i Q_{33}^i$ $\gamma_3^i = Q_{13}^i - \kappa^i Q_{33}^i$ $\gamma_4^i = (Q_{11}^i + 3Q_{33}^i)\gamma_0^i$
 $\gamma_5^i = Q_{11}^i + \kappa^i Q_{33}^i$ $\gamma_6^i = Q_{11}^i - \kappa^i Q_{33}^i$

Static:

Rotational:

Equivalent stress Al hub

Surface pressure

Optimal thickness design

Scheme	HS4 (t ₁)	T700 (t ₂)	T800 (t ₃)
I	30 mm	30 mm	30 mm
II	20 mm	30 mm	40 mm
III	40 mm	30 mm	20 mm
IV	20 mm	40 mm	30 mm
V	20 mm	50 mm	20 mm

Winding tension 160 N 200 N 125 N

Metal Shaft & Hub: SOLID186
 Composite Sleeve: SOLID46
 Contact Elements: CONTA170
 Winding tension of GFRP: 160 N
 Winding tension of T700: 200 N
 Winding tension of T800: 125 N
 Rotational speed: 30000 RPM

Experimental Devices

Experimental Validation

Filament winder able to provide high fiber tensions

Instruments for stress & strain test:

